

CODE INTERNATIONAL 2024

**ENHANCING HIKER SAFETY THROUGH A RELIABLE
TRACKING SYSTEM USING NRF24L01 TECHNOLOGY
IN REMOTE MOUNTAIN AREAS**

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Ternary
University of Brawijaya
Malang
2024

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Enhancing Hiker Safety Through A Reliable Tracking System Using Nrf24l01 Technology In Remote Mountain Areas

2. Sub-Theme : Technology and Information Systems

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**ENHANCING HIKER SAFETY THROUGH A RELIABLE TRACKING SYSTEM
USING NRF24L01 TECHNOLOGY IN REMOTE MOUNTAIN AREAS**

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With full awareness, I, as the team leader of Ternary, declare that the work titled above is my original creation and has never been published or won a similar competition elsewhere. I hereby confirm my participation in the CODE INTERNATIONAL 2024 competition and agree to all terms and conditions set by the committee. If a violation is proven, I accept disqualification from the competition as my responsibility.

October 1, 2024, Malang
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ENHANCING HIKER SAFETY THROUGH A RELIABLE TRACKING SYSTEM USING NRF24L01 TECHNOLOGY IN REMOTE MOUNTAIN AREAS

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ABSTRACT

Mountain hiking is one of the most favorite sport activities outdoors, resulting in a lot of physiological and psychic benefits; still, it holds serious risks, especially to inexperienced hikers. The capability of communicating one's own position or asking for help is extremely important in remote mountain areas with unreliable cellular coverage. This paper introduces MOUNTMAPS-a tracking system that utilizes NRF24L01 radio communication modules for enhancing the safety of hikers. These include a network of checkpoints deployed along the trails, each with receivers, with the hikers having transmitters that continuously update their location in real time to a centralized monitoring station. This research discusses advantages of the system using NRF24L01, as compared to conventional GPS, elaborating on how it proves to be more reliable at difficult terrains where GPS signals usually fail due to obstruction. The findings indicate that this system significantly enhances the general response of emergencies and thus safety during hiking in challenging environments.

Keyword: *Hiking, Hiker Safety, NRF24L01, Remote Monitoring, Tracking Systems*

INTRODUCTION

Background: Hiking is a popular outdoor activity that offers physical and mental benefits, but it can be dangerous for beginners due to the lack of experience, preparation, and navigation skills in remote mountainous regions. Inexperienced hikers face challenges such as getting lost, making navigational mistakes, and experiencing psychological stress. In 2013, Geraldine Largay went missing on the Appalachian Trail, highlighting the need for more effective tracking systems. The NRF24L01 systems is designed to overcome issues arising from rugged terrain by the architecture of its localized network. Embedding a number of receivers within certain intervals-for example, every hundred meters-across the area will reduce the distance each signal will need to travel, hence minimizing natural obstacles that normally degrade communication over long distances.

Problem Formulation:

1. How can we solve the issue of GPS signals not being supported in mountainous areas for tracking hikers?

Objective:

1. To find the solution of not supported GPS signal issue in mountainous areas for tracking hikers.

Benefits:

1. To track last location of hikers.
2. To help beginner hikers that has little experience in mountaineering.
3. To expedite the evacuation process in case of any unforeseen events.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research focuses on the creation of a tracking aid for climbing activities, where this tool functions like a checkpoint spread along the climbing route. Simply put, this device consists of 2 main components: a transmitter and a receiver. However, in its application, this device uses multiple transmitters and receivers. Each receiver can recognize or

connect with other transmitters. The following is a diagram of the procedure for making this tool.

Picture 1 : Research Procedure Graph

In Picture 1, we divided it into 5 stages as explained below:

A. Tools Preparing Stage

In this stage, we prepare the tools and materials needed for the creation of this device. Berikut merupakan alat dan bahan yang dibutuhkan:

Transmitter:

1. Arduino Nano
2. Nrf24101
3. Jumper Wire

Receiver:

1. Arduino Nano
2. Nrf24101
3. Jumper Wire

Other:

1. USB data type
2. Laptop/pc
3. Arduino IDE software

B. Hardware Making Stage

In this stage, we create the circuit diagram to connect all the necessary components. For this device, we made

2 separate devices that act as a transmitter and receiver. Here we

provide the circuit diagram for the transmitter:

Picture 2 : Transmitter Circuit Diagram

The following is the circuit diagram for the receiver:

Picture 3 : Receiver Circuit Diagram

C. Software Making Stage

This tool is programmed using the Arduino IDE software, which connects the laptop to the hardware via a data cable, then we need one more platform. Before that, we would like to display the pins that are connected between the modules.

TRANSMITTER	
Arduino Nano	Nrf24l01
3v3	3.3 v
GND	GND
D7	CE
D8	CSN
D11	MOSI
D12	-MISO
D13	SCK

Table 1 : Transmitter Pin Connection

Software development will be easy in the Arduino Integrated Development Environment and might not be that robust with regard to real-time issues such as signal interference or data loss. Testing also remains highly basic with respect to basic communication concepts, while negligible environmental testing stands concerning altitude or obstacles, which are important for system reliability. The complete performance analysis would be crucial, including the metrics on signal range and power consumption, to ensure that the system is viable. As these issues are resolved through further testing and refinement, exposure to outdoor environments will again be considered, and with the results, effectiveness can be augmented for

Receiver	
Node MCU	Nrf24l01
3v3	3.3 V
GND	GND
D7	CE
D8	CSN
D11	MOSI
D12	MISO
D13	SCK

Table 2 :Receiver Pin Connection

D. System Testing Stage

This stage aims to test how well the tool performs from the initial process to the final one. This test includes:

- a. Testing on nrf24l01. This test

involves whether the module is capable of sending and receiving signals.

- b. Testing the receiver with multiple transmitters. This test involves how a receiver can receive signals from various transmitters.

E. Analysis of Results

The research method analysis indicates the certain strengths and weaknesses of its practical usage in mountainous terrain. Usage of Arduino Nano and NRF24L01 will be cheap and easily available;

however, its range might be limited and therefore problematic for power management on difficult terrains. Hardware involved is somewhat practical to track the hikers: several transmitters and one receiver. However, durability aspects and power consumption under extreme conditions have to be further discussed.

the system.

RESEARCH RESULTS

After creating the device, we immediately conducted hardware testing. Here are the results from the testing of this device.

Transmitter	Can be recognized by	
	Receiver A	Receiver B
Transmitter A	✓	✓
Transmitter B	✓	✓

Table 3 :Result of communication between transmitter and receiver

DISCUSSION

We filled each device with the source code that we programmed using Arduino IDE. We used at least 2 transmitters and 2 receivers with the same module, namely nrf24l01. We named each transmitter as transmitter A and

transmitter B. The same goes for the receivers, which are receiver A and receiver B. Below is an explanation of the code lines for all devices. For transmitter A, the discussion of the source code is as follows.

```
#include <nRF24L01.h>
#include <printf.h>
#include <RF24.h>
#include <RF24_config.h>
#include <SPI.h>

RF24 radio(9, 10);
const byte address[6] = "00001"; //Add
address for transmitter B. Note: must be
different with transmitter A

void setup() {
Serial.begin(9600);
radio.begin();
radio.openWritingPipe(address);
radio.setPALevel(RF24_PA_MIN);
radio.stopListening();
}

void loop() {
const char text[] = "This is from transmitter
A"; //Change for transmitter B
radio.write(&text, sizeof(text));
Serial.println("Signal Sent: ini dari
transmitter 1");
delay(1000);
}
```

Dan untuk kode program receiver sebagai berikut.

```
#include <SPI.h>
#include <nRF24L01.h>
#include <RF24.h>

RF24 radio(9, 10)
const byte address1[6] = "00001";
const byte address2[6] = "00010";

void setup() {
Serial.begin(9600);
radio.begin();
radio.openReadingPipe(1, address1);
radio.openReadingPipe(2, address2);
```

```
radio.setPALevel(RF24_PA_MIN);
radio.startListening();
}

void loop(){
if (radio.available()) {
char text[32] = "";
uint8_t pipeNum;
bool received =
radio.available(&pipeNum);}
if (received) {
radio.read(&text, sizeof(text));
switch (pipeNum) {
case 1: Serial.println("Signal from
Transmitter A");
Break;
case 2: Serial.println("Signal from
Transmitter B");
break;
default:
Serial.println("Unknown pipe");
break;
}
}
```

We conducted two tests: one to check whether the module can send and receive messages. We used two modules, one as a transmitter and the other as a receiver. We tested them, and the results were very satisfactory. Both modules, the transmitter and the receiver, were able to send and receive messages effectively.

The second test involved assessing whether all receivers could receive signals from various transmitters. We also obtained satisfactory results from this test. The result is that all receivers are able to recognize the source of the signal they receive from the transmitter.

CONCLUSION

This research demonstrates that the described tracker system with NRF24L01 can be a powerful solution for tracking hikers in remote mountainous areas. Mountain hiking, on one hand, offers a number of physical and mental benefits; on the other hand, it carries obvious risks, particularly for those less experienced hikers who perhaps are confronted with difficult-to-navigate terrain for the first

time. However, conventional GPS is operationally limited in these areas, because the signal is usually obstructed either by cliffs or dense forests of tall trees. And with partial signal reception alone, accuracy concerning your location may be lost, or it may even cause a complete loss of signal. Besides, reliance on cellular networks when coverage at such remote locations is high increases risks even higher.

While the GPS systems were quite costly and power-consuming, this technology ensures a low-cost and low-power solution. NRF24L01 exploits the short-range communication between the transmitter carried by hikers and the receivers placed along mountain trails to minimize the terrain-induced disruptions of the signal. This gives this system the great advantage of tracking independently from cellular networks even in the most remote areas.

The modular design of the NRF24L01 system allows ease in adapting it into the landscape, thus maintaining communication and removing the requirement for a line-of-sight between transmitter and receiver—a limitation common in GPS-based systems. Additionally, the low power consumption of the system makes it ideal for long-duration hikes where frequent changes of batteries are highly impracticable.

The conclusion is that the NRF24L01-based tracking system is one of the practical and effective methods used for the protection of the safety of hikers in remote mountainous areas. It provides superior services compared to conventional systems since it achieves the goal of real-time location tracking. Additionally, further research and improvement might be directed at increasing the signal strength and adaptability of the system in more extreme

terrain in order to enhance efficacy and ensure the absolute safety of all hikers.

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BIODATA ATTACHMENT
COMPETITION OF OUTSTANDING CREATIVITY AND EXPLORATION
2024

Team Name : Ternary

Title : **ENHANCING HIKER SAFETY THROUGH A
RELIABLE TRACKING SYSTEM USING
NRF24L01 TECHNOLOGY IN REMOTE
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